

Effects of Flexural Rigidity Ratio of Footing Beam to Column of Cylindrical Lattice Shell Roofs on Dynamic Interactions with Multi-layered Soil

Koki KAWAI^{*a}, Chihiro ITOYAMA^b, Tomohiko KUMAGAI^a, Hiroko SUZUKI^c

^{*} Dept. of Arch. and Urbanism, Graduate School of Sci. and Tech., Meiji University
1-1-1 Higashimita Tama-ku Kawasaki-shi Kanagawa 214-8571 Japan
koki771104@outlook.jp

^b Former Dept. of Arch. and Urbanism, Graduate School of Sci. and Tech., Meiji University
^c Dept. of Arch., Faculty of Creative Engineering, Chiba Institute of Technology

Abstract

In the seismic response of buildings, it is understood that phase differences and amplitude differences arise due to the heterogeneity of the soil, and that the dynamic interaction between the soil and the structure differs. The properties of the soil are one of the factors that influence the seismic response of structures, and to analyze this effect, it is necessary to consider the coupled effect with the soil in seismic response analysis. Therefore, this paper is intended as an investigation of the effects of the flexural rigidity ratio k of the footing beams to the columns of spatial structures built on horizontally divided soil, on the free vibration characteristics and the seismic response behavior of the structures, taking into account the coupling with the soil. In addition, the differences in response characteristics with and without coupling to the soil are also investigated.

Keywords: Spatial Structure, Foundation Structure, Flexural Rigidity Ratio, Heterogeneous Soil, Dynamic Interaction, Seismic Response Behavior.

1. Introduction

The several researches have been conducted on the dynamic interaction structures and soil in seismic response (Kimura et al[1], Itoyama et al[2] and Su and Kato[3]). However, studies focusing on the flexural rigidity of footing beams are limited (Kimura et al[1] and Itoyama et al[2]). Therefore, In this paper, the focus is on cylindrical lattice shell roofs, and the influence of the flexural rigidity ratio k of footing beam to column of the spatial structure, which stands on a soil model divided horizontally, on its vibrational characteristics and seismic response behavior is examined, considering the coupling with the soil. In this analysis, the flexural rigidity of the columns or footing beams is considered within the range where the rotational boundary condition of the shallow foundation can be treated as rigid. Furthermore, the effects of changing the surface soil conditions are explored, particularly when the foundation is coupled with soft or hard soil. Additionally, the study compares the seismic response behavior with and without considering the coupling between the building and the soil, and with the soil treated as rigid, in order to investigate the conditions under which the consideration of soil-structure interaction becomes necessary.

2. Analysis models of structure and summary of numerical analysis methods

The analysis model and model name are shown in Figure 1. The target structure is cylindrical lattice shell roofs, and the lattice member cross-section is ϕ -267.4 \times 3.5~6.0. The roof structure and the lower structure are pin-connected. The node positions and node names of the foundation are shown in Figure 2. The material specifications of the members are shown in Tables 1 and 2. The independent foundation

and footing beams are made of concrete, and the foundation and the column base are rigidly connected. The value of k in Table 2 is the flexural rigidity ratio of the column and foundation beam, calculated using Eq.(1).

$$k = k_g / k_c \quad (1)$$

Here, k_g and k_c are the footing beam bending stiffness and column bending stiffness, respectively, which are calculated from Eqs. (2), (3).

$$k_g = E_g \times I_g / L_g \quad (2)$$

$$k_c = E_c \times I_c / L_c \quad (3)$$

where, E is the young's modulus, I is the area moment of inertia and L is the member length. The subscript g represents the footing beam and c represents the column.

Figure 1: Target structure

Figure 2: Node positions of the foundation

Table 1: Material specifications of columns

Type of columns	a	b
Slenderness ratio λ	28.1	28.8
Outer diameter D [cm]	60.96	60.96
Thickness t [cm]	0.65	2.10
Cross-sectional area A [cm ²]	123.2	387.4
Moment of inertia I [$\times 10^4$ cm ⁴]	5.60	16.80

Table 2: Material specifications of columns

Flexural rigidity ratio	i		ii		iii		iv	
	$k=1.714$		$k=5.786$		$k=13.71$		$k=26.79$	
Type of foundation beams	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
Width B_b [cm]	40.0	52.6	60.0	79.0	80.0	105	100	132
Height H_b [cm]	120	158	120	158	120	158	120	158
Cross-sectional area A_b [cm ²]	4800	8313	7200	12470	9600	16627	12000	20784
Moment of inertia I_b [$\times 10^4$ cm ⁴]	64.0	192	216	648	512	1536	1000	3000

Figure 3 and Figure 4 shows the top three dominant eigen modes of the cylindrical lattice shell roofs under study. The natural frequency f (Hz) and effective mass ratio (%) are also shown.

Figure 3: Dominant eigenmode of the structure (α, β soil spring support)

Figure 4: Dominant eigenmode of the structure (γ soil spring support)

The numerical analysis is performed using the finite element analysis program ANSYS 2023 R1. The analysis method is time-history response analysis considering geometric nonlinearity, and the numerical integration method used is the Newmark β method ($\beta = 0.25$). Rayleigh damping is applied, with damping constants set to 2% for the first and second modes of the structure, and 2.5% at 0.5 Hz and 6 Hz for the soil.

3. Summary of soil models

Figure 5 shows a simplified cross-sectional diagram of the analysis model, and Figure 6 shows the element division in the finite element method. The soil consists of clay for layers ① to ③ and gravel for layer ④. The N values for each layer are shown in Table 3. A dashpot is created between the analyzed soil, the free soil, and the bottom surface of the soil to represent the semi-infinite nature of the soil. The foundation and the soil are connected by soil springs, shown in Table 4 (Japan road association [4]).

Figure 5: Simplified cross-sectional diagram of analysis model

Figure 6: Element division in finite element method

Table 3: N values for each layer

N value	α	β	γ
N_1	5	5	10
N_2	10	20	5
N_3		30	
N_4		45	

Table 4: Coefficients of subgrade reaction

N value of the surface layer	5	10
E_0 [kN/m ²]	14000	28000
k_V [kN/m ²]	22496	44992
k_S [kN/m ²]	5624	11248

4. Input seismic waves and soil response

The input earthquake motion is set such that the target acceleration response spectrum is twice the earthquake motion specified in the Ministry of Construction Notification No.1461, with the phase being random. The analysis time is set to 10 seconds. The earthquake motion is input in the horizontal x-direction at the bottom of both the analysis soil and the free soil using the Large Mass Method. Figure

7 shows the acceleration response spectra of the input wave and the wave observed at the soil surface, while Figure 8 shows the maximum response acceleration at a point within the soil, located vertically downward from the origin O', for the Si_a_* and Si_b_* models. The difference in response due to variations in substructure components is small. In Figure 8, a difference is observed in the second layer depending on the N-value, with smaller N-values leading to larger responses. However, the difference in response at the soil surface is minimal.

Figure 7: Acceleration response spectra of input wave and wave observed at soil surface ($h=2.5\%$) (Flexural rigidity ratio i model)

Figure 8: Maximum response accelerations at points within soil

5. Effects of the flexural rigidity of columns and foundation beams on seismic response behavior

Figure 9 shows maximum relative response acceleration on line AOA' to the soil surface. In the γ soil, the response of the b model is larger compared to that of the a model. Additionally, significant differences are observed based on the N value. This may be due to the fact that in α soil, low order modes such as the 4th order modes shown in Figures 3 and 4 are excited in both the a and b models, while in γ soil, low order modes are excited in the a model and higher order modes such as the 35th and

27th order modes shown in Figures 3 and 4 are excited in the b model. Figure 10 shows the relationship between the flexural rigidity ratio k and the maximum rotation angle around the y-axis of the foundation. The rotation angle of the foundation is calculated using the following equation.

$$\Delta y = u_{y_{in}} - u_{y_{out}} \quad (4)$$

$$rad = \arctan(\Delta y / L) \quad (5)$$

Where, $u_{y_{in}}$ and $u_{y_{out}}$ represent the vertical displacements at the inner and outer sides of the foundation, shown in Figure 2, respectively, and L is the dimension of the foundation in the beam direction, which is 2 meters. At node a', as k increases, the maximum rotation angle increases, excluding the effect of the γ soil, but at node g', the rotation angle decreases regardless of the soil. Furthermore, the difference in the maximum rotation angle between the a and b models is significant under γ soil conditions.

Figure 9: Maximum relative response accelerations on line AOA' to soil surface (vertical direction)

Figure 10: Relationships between flexural rigidity ratios k and maximum rotation angles around the y-axis of foundation

6. Effects of the presence or absence of coupling on seismic response behavior

When the coupling with the soil is not considered, in the case of soil spring support, the acceleration at the origin O' is directly applied to each soil spring of the structure. In the case of fixed support, the acceleration at the origin O' is directly applied to each foundation of the structure. Figure 11 illustrates

the relationship between the flexural rigidity ratio k and the maximum rotation angle around the y-axis of the foundation. Regardless of the model, the difference between the presence or absence of coupling is small, and the magnitude of this difference varies depending on the N-value of the soil. Figure 12 shows the maximum relative response accelerations on line AOA' to the soil surface, while Figure 13 shows the root mean square of the vertical response acceleration time history for all nodes on the roof surface in each model over all analysis steps. In the a model, the response increases in the following order: soil spring support, with coupling, fixed support. In the b model, the response in the case of soil spring support exceeds that with coupling. In the a model, the response is larger for the α and β soils, while in the b model, the response is larger for the γ soil. In the a model, there is no consistent trend in the response based on the flexural rigidity ratio k , whereas in the b model, the response increases as k becomes larger. As a result, it is possible to understand the difference from the seismic responses in fixed support, which is often used in structural design.

Figure 11: Relationships between flexural rigidity ratios k and maximum rotation angles around y-axis of foundation (Node a')

Figure 12: Maximum relative response accelerations on line AOA' to soil surface (vertical direction)

Figure 13: Root mean square values of time history vertical accelerations for each model

7. Conclusions

It is concluded as follows, from the above results.

- 1) The differences in the acceleration response spectrum of surface waves and the maximum response acceleration in the soil due to differences in the members for the substructure are small, while the differences in these responses due to differences in the soil conditions are large.
- 2) The differences in vertical response acceleration and foundation rotation angle between the a and b models become larger when the N-value of the surface layer is high.
- 3) The root-mean-square of the time history vertical response accelerations for all analysis steps at all nodes of the roof is greater in the model without the coupling supported by soil springs than in the model with the coupling. Regarding the differences in response due to the ratio k , the responses increase with increasing k in models with large flexural rigidity of the substructure.

References

- [1] T. Kimura, Y. Shamoto, K. Matsui, H. Mano, M. Mori, and S. Nakai “Effect of foundation girder stiffness on pile response during earthquake,” *Journal of structural and construction engineering (Transactions of AIJ)*, Vol.72, No.618, pp. 41-48. 2007.8. (in Japanese)
- [2] C. Itoyama, T. Kumagai, I. Takahashi, H. Suzuki, “Effects of Differences in Free Vibration Characteristics of Cylindrical Lattice Shell Roofs due to Dimensions of Foundation Structures on Dynamic Interactions with Multi-layered Grounds,” *Summaries of Technical Papers of Annual Meeting Architectural Institute of Japan*, B-1, pp. 737-738. 2023.9. (in Japanese)
- [3] L. Su, S. Kato, “The research on the seismic responses of the large span structures considering the irregularity of soil layers,” *Summaries of Technical Papers of Annual Meeting Architectural Institute of Japan*, B-2, pp. 499-500. 2001.9. (in Japanese)
- [4] Japan road association, “Specifications for highway bridges,” Japan road association, 2012